

5-Chloro-3-ethyl-6-methyl-2-benzofurylacetic Acid

D. S. Deorha and (Miss) Padma Gupta

Interaction of 4-[(5'-chloro-3'-ethyl-6'-methyl-2'-benzofuranyl)methylene]-2-phenyloxazolin-5-one and hydrazine hydrate affords α -benzamido- β -(5-chloro-3-ethyl-6-methyl-2-benzofuryl)acrylohydrazide. The hydrazide is converted to the azide by nitrous acid and the latter, on heating in benzene, yields 4-[(5'-chloro-3'-ethyl-6'-methyl-2'-benzofuranyl)methyl]-6-phenyl-2H-1,3,5-oxadiazine-2-one, hydrolysis of which furnishes 5-chloro-3-ethyl-6-methyl-2-benzofurylacetic acid.

Recently Jennings¹ explored a reaction for the conversion of *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde to *m*-nitrophenylacetic acid. The procedure involves conversion of the azlactone of the aldehyde to the hydrazide, which furnishes the azide by reacting with nitrous acid. The azide decomposes in hot benzene solution to afford an oxadiazine, hydrolysis of which provides *m*-nitrophenylacetic acid. In the present investigation, the reaction has been extended to the synthesis of 5-chloro-3-ethyl-6-methyl-2-benzofurylacetic acid.

Prepared from 5-chloro-2-hydroxy-4-methylpropiophenone², 4-chloro-5-methyl-2-propionylphenoxyacetic acid (II: R=H) is converted to 5-chloro-3-ethyl-6-methylbenzofuran (I: R=H), which by Gattermann's method furnishes 5-chloro-3-ethyl-2-formyl-6-methylbenzofuran (I: R=CHO) in poor yields. The method explored by Bisagni *et al.*³, employing dimethylformamide and phosphorus oxychloride, has, however, been used for the formylation with a better yield of the formyl derivative (I: R=CHO). The orientation of the formyl derivative has been confirmed by oxidation to carboxylic acid (I: R=COOH), identical

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 1512.

2. Kindler and Oelschläger, *Chem. Ber.*, 1954, 87, 197.

3. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 3699.

with the specimen formed by cyclisation of (II: R=Et), and subsequent hydrolysis of the resulting ester (I: R=CO₂Et). The 2-formylbenzofuran is then converted to the azlactone (III), which with hydrazine hydrate yields the hydrazide (IV: R=NHNH₂). The hydrazide on heating with nitrous acid forms the azide (IV: R=N₃). The azide on heating in benzene undergoes the Curtius rearrangement to form oxadiazino (V), furnishing 5-chloro-3-ethyl-6-methyl-2-benzofurylacetic acid (I: R=CH₂COOH) on hydrolysis. The azlactone on hydrolysis provides poor yields of the pyruvic acid (I: R=CH₂CO.COOH), oxidation of which to the benzofurylacetic acid (I: R=CH₂COOH) is very difficult to control. Jennings' method¹ was thus found more expeditious in spite of greater number of steps involved in it.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl 4-Chloro-5-methyl-2-propionylphenoxyacetate (II: R = Et).—A mixture of 5-chloro-2-hydroxy-4-methylpropiophenone (16.2 g.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (40 g.), ethyl chloroacetate (10.2 g.), potassium iodide (0.1 g.), and dry acetone (150 ml) was heated under reflux for 18 hr. and then filtered. The potassium salts were washed with hot acetone and the combined acetone filtrates distilled. The residue was crystallised from ethanol in colorless plates (20 g.), m.p. 83-84°. (Found: Cl, 12.62. C₁₄H₁₇O₄Cl requires Cl, 12.45%).

The 2,4-*DNP* was obtained from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 202-203°. (Found: N, 11.89. C₂₀H₂₁O₇N₄Cl requires N, 12.05%).

4-Chloro-5-methyl-2-propionylphenoxyacetic Acid (II: R=H).—The above ester (10 g.) was heated with 5% NaOH solution (100 ml) in ethanol (15 ml) under reflux for 2 hr. The cooled solution was diluted with water and filtered. The filtrate on treating with HCl (conc.) furnished the phenoxyacetic acid, crystallising from glacial acetic acid in colorless needles (8.3 g.), m.p. 139-41°. (Found: Cl, 13.97. C₁₂H₁₃O₄Cl requires Cl, 13.81%). Its 2,4-*DNP* separated from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 179°. (Found: N, 13.03. C₁₈H₁₇O₇N₄Cl requires N, 12.82%).

5-Chloro-3-ethyl-6-methylbenzofuran (I: R=H).—A mixture of the preceding acid (14.2 g.), anhydrous sodium acetate (25 g.), and acetic anhydride (50 ml) was heated at 160° (oil bath) for 4 hr., cooled, and poured on cold water (200 ml). After 24 hr., the product was extracted with benzene, the extract washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate to remove acids, and dried (Na₂SO₄). Removal of benzene and distillation of the residue furnished the benzofuran as a colorless oil (8 g.), b.p. 262-63°. (Found: Cl, 18.56. C₁₁H₁₁OCl requires Cl, 18.21%).

5-Chloro-2-formyl-3-ethyl-6-methylbenzofuran (I: R=CHO).—The above benzofuran (1 g.) was added to an ice-cold mixture of dimethylformamide (7 ml) and freshly distilled POCl₃ (3 ml). The mixture was heated on a water bath for 4 hr., cooled, diluted with water, and neutralised with sodium bicarbonate. After 2 hr., the product was extracted with ether, washed with water, dried (Na₂SO₄), and recovered by evaporation of the solvent. The residue was crystallised from ethanol in light yellow needles, m.p. 91-92°. (Found: Cl, 16.11. C₁₂H₁₁O₂Cl requires Cl, 15.92%). The 2,4-*DNP* separated from ethanol as deep red crystals, m.p. 230-32°. (Found: N, 14.23. C₁₈H₁₅O₇N₄Cl requires N, 13.91%).

4-[(5'-Chloro-3'-ethyl-6'-methyl-2'-benzofuranyl)methylene]-2-phenyloxazolin-5-one (III).—A mixture of the benzofuran (I: R=CHO) (4.8 g.), hippuric acid (7 g.), anhydrous sodium acetate (4 g.), and acetic anhydride (25 ml) was heated on a water bath for 2 hr., diluted with ethanol (100 ml), and left overnight. The crystalline oxazolone was filtered and crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles (5.5 g.), m.p. 200-201°. (Found: Cl, 9.81. $C_{21}H_{16}O_3NCl$ requires Cl, 9.69%).

α -Benzamido- β -(5-chloro-3-ethyl-6-methyl-2-benzofuryl)acryloylhydrazide (IV; R = $NHNH_2$).—The finely powdered oxazolone (III, 5 g.) in ethanol (150 ml) was treated with 99% hydrazine hydrate (1.3 ml) and stirred until the colour was discharged. The solid was collected and crystallised from ethanol in light yellow needles, m.p. 205°. (Found: Cl, 9.01. $C_{21}H_{20}O_3N_3Cl$ requires Cl, 8.91%).

4-[(5'-Chloro-3'-ethyl-6'-methyl-2'-benzofuranyl)methyl]-6-phenyl-2H-1,3,5-oxadiazin-2-one (V).—To the cold solution of the preceding hydrazide (1g.) in glacial acetic acid (25 ml) was added slowly a solution of sodium nitrite (0.5 g.) in minimum amount of water, the temperature being kept below 10°. After $\frac{1}{2}$ hr., the yellow crystalline precipitate was filtered, washed with water, and dried in air.

The crude azide (m.p. 131°, decomp.) (4 g.) was then extracted from a soxhlet thimble with benzene (75 ml). When concentrated and cooled, the benzene extract deposited the oxadiazine. It was recrystallised from benzene in yellow silky needles (3.5 g.), m.p. 232-33°. (Found: Cl, 9.62. $C_{21}H_{17}O_3N_2Cl$ requires Cl, 9.31%).

The oxadiazine was also obtained by heating the azide. It first melted with effervescence and then solidified (225°). It was recrystallised from benzene in yellow needles (0.7 g.), m.p. and mixed m.p. 232-33°.

5-Chloro-3-ethyl-6-methyl-2-benzofurylpyruvic Acid (I: R= $CH_2CO.COOH$).—The oxazolone (1 g.) was boiled gently under reflux with a mixture of 20% solution of KOH (20 ml) till the solution cleared. The condenser was then removed and hydrolysis was completed by gentle boiling till free of ammonia (smell). During the later part of the reaction, the volume of the solution was kept at 20 ml by occasional addition of water. The solution was diluted with water (50 ml) and filtered. The cold filtrate was acidified with HCl (conc.) and warmed on a steam bath to 60°. In this form the pyruvic acid separated in a granular form and was easily filtered. The benzoic acid formed in the reaction remained in solution. The pyruvic acid was separated and crystallised from aqueous ethanol (1:1) in pale yellow needles (0.2 g.), m.p. 205°. (Found: Cl, 12.82. $C_{14}H_{13}O_4Cl$ requires Cl, 12.63%).

5-Chloro-3-ethyl-6-methyl-2-benzofurylpyruvic Acid (I: R= CH_2COOH).—(a). A mixture of the oxadiazine (38 g.), acetic acid (400 ml), and 5N-HCl (40 ml) was boiled till complete dissolution and full discharge of the colour. Subsequent dilution with water precipitated 2-benzofurylacetic and benzoic acids. The latter was leached out with water at 60°, leaving the crude 2-benzofurylacetic acid, which was crystallised from aqueous ethanol (1:1) in colorless needles (22.7 g.), m.p. 153°. (Found: Cl, 14.23. $C_{13}H_{13}O_3Cl$ requires Cl, 14.03%).

(b). A solution of the crude pyruvic acid (18.7 g.) in 10% aqueous solution of KOH (50 ml) was mixed with hydrogen peroxide (20 ml of 100 vol.) at 0°, warmed until effervescence

began, cooled to 0°, diluted with ice-water, and acidified with HCl (conc.). Thus precipitated, 5-chloro-3-ethyl-6-methyl-2-benzofurylacetic acid crystallised from aqueous ethanol (1:1) in colorless needles (6 g.), m.p. and mixed m.p. with above sample 153°.

The *methyl ester*, prepared by diazomethane, crystallised from benzene in colorless needles, m.p. 63°. (Found: Cl, 13.02. $C_{14}H_{15}O_3Cl$ requires Cl, 13.29%).

5-Chloro-3-ethyl-6-methylbenzofuran-2-carboxylic Acid (I: R=COOH).—(a). The ester (II: R=Et) (1.1g.) was dissolved in ethanol (10 ml) and a solution of sodium ethoxide (0.2 g. Na in 10ml dry ethanol) was added. The solution was heated on a water bath for 15 min. and then diluted with water (20 ml). The clear solution was acidified with 5*N*-HCl and the product crystallised from glacial acetic acid in colorless prisms (0.35 g.), m.p. 230°. (Found: Cl, 15.06. $C_{12}H_{11}O_3Cl$ requires Cl, 14.85%).

(b) To the benzofuran (I: R=CHO) (1g.), dissolved in purified acetone (30 ml), $KMnO_4$ (0.6 g.) in water (20 ml) was added. The solution slowly deposited manganese dioxide and after 18 hr., this was removed by means of sulphur dioxide. The solution was diluted with water and the white solid separating was collected, dissolved in ether, and extracted with sodium bicarbonate solution. The alkaline extract on acidification with 5*N*-HCl provided the acid (0.5 g.), which was crystallised from acetic acid; m.p. 230°, undepressed by admixture with the above sample.

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